

Microstructure and Immersion Corrosion study of stir-casted magnesium alloy AZ91 in 3.5 wt. % NaCl solution

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Abstract

Present study aimed to evaluate the corrosion properties of produced magnesium alloy AZ91 when immersed in 3.5 wt. % NaCl solution. Conventional and novel stir casting method was used to prepare magnesium alloy AZ91. The entire process was conducted under protective atmosphere of argon and sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) mixture. Then the samples were subjected to T6-Ageing heat treatment. The stir-casted samples corrosion properties were analysed in the atmospheric condition. The XRD and SEM analysis were carried out to analyse the microstructure and surface morphology of samples. Outcome indicated that presence of primary α -Mg phase and the secondary Mg₁₇Al₁₂ intermetallic phases. The surface morphology indicated that uniform mixture of individual elements. The corrosive medium 3.5 wt. % NaCl solution was considered for this present study. The corrosion rate of samples was carried out in three different durations 24 hrs, 48 hrs and 72 hrs respectively. All the experimental results demonstrated the magnesium alloy exhibited significant corrosion (material loss) when exposed to 3.5 wt. % NaCl corrosive medium. The maximum corrosion rate was 0.022042 g/hr reported for 72 hr sample. This indicated that appropriate corrosion-resistant materials or secondary process is required to improve better corrosion resistance for specific applications.

Keywords: magnesium, stir casting, T6-ageing heat treatment, immersion corrosion, electrochemical corrosion

I. INTRODUCTION

Investigations on corrosion properties is one of the emerging research areas, particularly for magnesium-based materials [1]. Magnesium is one the predominant light weight material possessed good mechanical characteristics; however, it suffered from poor corrosion resistance properties [2]. Palaniappan N et al. 2020 [3] analyzed selenium and graphene oxide coated magnesium alloy AZ13 for its corrosion properties. And stated selenium composite materials possessed low potential peak and it can act as an anode material for a sodium ion battery. In addition, the samples microstructure was characterized by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Ruhi et al. 2022 [4] studied electrochemical corrosion behavior of pure magnesium. The immersion corrosion test was performed with chloride (NaCl) concentrations in the range of 0 - 1500 mM. In this work magnesium corrosion and phosphate precipitation were analysed both in acidic and alkaline medium varies pH value from 4 to 8. This study has reported that higher corrosion rate was obtained at pH 8 due to magnesium dissolution. The degradation response of AZ91 alloy was investigated by Zhichao Liu et al. 2025 [5] and observed that degradation layer consist of three distinct sub-layers: poor crystalline layer (PCL) layer, amorphous layer (AL) and a hybrid layer (HL) layer. And results demonstrated that the corrosion resistance of magnesium alloy AZ91 is enhanced due to the presence of the compact PCL layer, the uniform distribution of the intermetallic compound $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ phase and formation of impenetrable layered double hydroxide (LDH) at the corrosion interface. Chuan wei Yan 2023 [6] analysed corrosion behavior of Mg alloy AZ91D through electrochemical behavior in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution anodized. In addition electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, potential dynamic polarization curve were examined to understand the corrosion behavior. And microstructures of samples were examined through scanning electron microscope. Both corroded and before corrosion experiment. Pardo et al. 2008 [7] also indicated that commercial magnesium such as AZ91D alloy and AZ80 were exhibited better corrosion resistance due to fine β -phase ($Mg_{17}Al_{12}$) which were key factor for lowering the corrosion rate. Sun et al. 2009 [8] investigated corrosion resistance aluminium sheet alclad and extruded aluminium alloy 2024 and 7075 were investigated by weight loss method, and loss in mechanical strength over 20 years. The outcome

illustrated the inner cladding layer on alclad material possesses higher corrosion resistance. Especially in coastal and chemical industrial atmosphere extruded 2024 alloys were suffered by severe exfoliation hence deterioration of mechanical properties were observed. In addition, corroded surface morphology and elements were analysed by XRD, SEM, and EDS. Liu et al. 2024 [9] compared the corrosion rate of aluminium oxide surface Al-O (1 1 1) with 7A46 aluminium alloy. In this research work 1.0 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) solutions were used as electrolyte solution. The electrochemical corrosion test, surface analysis, and density calculations had been carried out. The outcome showed that the corrosion current density (*i*) is around $\sim 80.62 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in HCl solution and $104.21 \mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in H₂SO₄ solution. However, outcome indicate that the Al alloy 2024 alloy is not compatible with this material due to formation of NaAlCO₃(OH)₂ in contact with air.

Proton et al. 2014 [10] demonstrated the influence of artificial ageing heat treatment on the corrosion behavior of the produced 2050 Al–Cu–Li aluminium alloy. This resulted that intergranular to intragranular and reduced the corrosion potential of the alloy. Ujah et al. 2024 [11] reviewed recent publications on corrosion characteristics of HEAs processed by SPS technique. And authors demonstrated that top notch technique produces corrosion resistant phases and homogenous microstructure. From the study, it was revealed that incorporation of some elements (Al, Cr, Ti) into HEAs can improve their corrosion resistance, while addition of some others can reduce their brittleness and enhance their stability and formability. Uerdingen 2005 [12] studied corrosion behavior of carbon steel, austenitic stainless steel, nickel-based alloy C22, copper, brass and aluminium (AlMg3) in seven ionic liquids (ILs) with different chemical structure under flow conditions at temperatures up to 90 °C. The outcome revealed copper and brass generally suffer from severe attack in ionic liquids media at higher temperatures. However, it was demonstrated that corrosion inhibition is possible. Patel et al. 2016 [13] studied the compatibility of molten salts with the structural alloys and materials corrosion has been of real concern at such temperatures (600 - 900°C). Emphasis has also been given on the material composition of the oxide films (corrosion) products on alloys of interest in wide a range of melts. This article deliberates corrosion characteristics mainly at high temperatures and long exposures.

From the previous literatures available indicates that the material development and corrosion studies turn out to be an essential part of research. The corrosion kinetics of modern materials in variety of molten salts with focus on reaction mechanisms and corrosion products is investigated by scientists around the globe. And molten salt corrosion has been predominantly studied by gravimetric, electrochemical techniques and, morphology and chemical analysis of corrosion products by means of XRD, SEM. In addition, very few literatures only available for stir casted magnesium alloy corrosion behavior of magnesium alloy through 3.5 wt.% NaCl salt solution. Hence present study aimed to understand the corrosion characteristics in terms of mass loss of stir-casted magnesium alloy AZ91 through immersion corrosion test.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Material Preparation

The samples for present work are prepared through novel stir casting process. Raw materials such as 9 wt. % pure aluminium, 1 wt. % zinc, 0.5 wt. % manganese and pure magnesium for balance weight percent are used to prepare the AZ91 alloy. Electric resistance heater used to melt the raw materials and stirrer allowed to rotate 500 rpm to mix the molten slurry uniformly. Entire process was carried out in the inert gas medium (mixture of SF₆ and Ar). Then molten material poured into preheated mold (200 °C), and allowed to cool to attain room temperature in open atmosphere [2]. After preparation of mold casting, samples for microstructure and for immersion corrosion test were processed through wire cut EDM method. Mn added to improve the ductility and mechanical property. Fig. 01 indicates the material preparation through stir casting process. Fig. 02 showed the stir casted magnesium alloy AZ91. Then as cast magnesium alloy had been subjected to low temperature ageing heat treatment in the muffle furnace. Solution heat treatment was carried out at 350 °C and low temperature ageing performed at 100 °C. Fig. 03 (a) represents corrosion test samples and Fig. 03 (b) indicates the CAD model for immersion corrosion test and Fig. 04 showed the wire cut EDM processed samples for microstructure analysis (XRD and SEM). Average of three results are considered for the corrosion properties.

Fig. 01 Preparation of cast metal

Fig. 02 Produced stir-casted sample

Fig. 03 Samples for (a) corrosion test (b) CAD model of sample

Fig. 04 Samples for microstructure prepared through EDM

2.2 Immersion corrosion test

The immersion corrosion test was conducted on the prepared cylindrical shaped samples. In order to measure the material loss or corrosion rate of sample, 3.5 g laboratory NaCl salt was mixed with 100 g distilled water in the atmospheric condition. The mass of salt and samples were measured in the weight balance having accuracy 0.001 g. Then the samples were immersed in the separate glass beakers contains 3.5 wt. % NaCl solution, and measured weight loss after one day (24 hrs), two days (48 hrs) and three days (72 hrs) respectively. After the specified period of immersion, the samples were taken out from the beakers and allowed to dry and cleaned, then again, the weight of samples were measured. From the loss of weight, the degradation rate or corrosion rate was calculated using the equation 01 [14].

Calculation Formula for corrosion rate (CR):

$$\text{Corrosion rate (CR)} = \frac{(m_{t_i} - m_{t_f})}{t_f - t_i} \quad (\text{g/hr}) \quad (1)$$

Where,

m_{t_i} = Initial mass in g

m_{t_f} = Final mass in g

$t_f - t_i$ = Time duration in hr

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 X-Ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of pure magnesium and prepared AZ91 are illustrated in Fig. 05 (a) and Fig. 05 (b) respectively. XRD image of pure magnesium indicates highest clear peaks of pure Mg were identified at an angle 36.5° with 8000 counts (a.u). Clear peaks validate the crystal form of pure magnesium. Clear peaks of same metal pure magnesium have identified at 35° , 62.5° with 1000 counts (a.u). Clear peaks of same metal pure magnesium have identified at 2° , 57.5° , 67.5° and 70° with counts 250 (a.u). Fig. 03 (b) represented the XRD analysis for the produced magnesium alloy. XRD studies of AZ91 included XRD patterns confirm the presence of the primary α -Mg phase and the secondary $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ intermetallic phase.

Fig. 05 XRD image of (a) pure Mg (b) produced magnesium alloy AZ91

3.2 SEM analysis

Fig. 06 demonstrated the surface morphology of the AZ91 alloy (T6 heat treated) sample. The surface morphology was analysed through SEM. The distribution of primary phase and secondary phase $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ are visible in the SEM image. In addition, that the surface morphology indicates the preparation method stir casting is suitable for the preparation of magnesium alloy AZ91.

Fig. 06 SEM image of produced Mg alloy

3.3 Discussion on Corrosion Properties

Fig. 07 Immersion corrosion test (a) 24 hrs (b) 48 hrs (c) 72 hrs

Fig. 08 Immersion corrosion test (a) 24 hrs (b) 48 hrs (c) 72 hrs

Fig. 07 represents the experimental works carried out to evaluate the corrosion rate of sample. In addition, Fig. 08 (a) indicates the image of corroded samples after one day (24 hrs), Fig. 08 (b) represents corroded samples after two days and Fig. 08 (c) indicates the corroded samples after three days (72 hrs) respectively. The immersion corrosion test results showed significant mass loss due to 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution. Initially, the samples possessed masses of 1.986 g, 2.125 g, and 2.197 g, but after exposure to the corrosive medium (table 1), their masses decreased to 1.72 g, 1.25 g, and 0.61 g, respectively (table 2). This reduction demonstrated that varying degrees of material degradation, with the third sample experiencing the higher corrosion rate. The differences in mass loss could be attributed to variations in material composition, exposure time, or the aggressiveness of the corrosive medium.

Table 1 Mass Calculation (Before Corrosion)

	Trial - 1	Trial - 2	Trial - 3	Average (g)
Sample (AZ91)	(g)	(g)	(g)	
sample-1 (24 hrs)	1.738	2.233	1.935	1.986
sample-2 (48 hrs)	2.125	1.855	1.603	2.125
sample-3 (72 hrs)	2.197	2.148	1.938	2.197

Table 2 Mass Calculation (After Corrosion)

	Trial - 1	Trial - 2	Trial - 3	Average (g)
Sample (AZ91)	(g)	(g)	(g)	
sample-1 (24 hrs)	1.72	1.72	1.72	1.72
sample-2 (48 hrs)	1.25	1.26	1.25	1.25
sample-3 (72 hrs)	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61

Equation 01 was used to measure the degradation rate or material loss or corrosion rate of present sample and represented in table 3. This formula determines the rate at which material is lost due to corrosion over time, expressed in grams per hour (g/hr). The results for different samples show that corrosion rates vary with time. For Sample-1, exposed for 24 hours, the rate was 0.01108 g/hr, indicating a slower initial corrosion process. In contrast, Sample-2, which underwent 48 hours of exposure, had a higher corrosion rate of 0.018 g/hr, suggesting an acceleration in material degradation. Sample-3, after 72 hours, also had higher rate of 0.022042 g/hr, which could indicate the material exhibited significant corrosion in the salt medium 3.5 wt.% NaCl.

These variations in corrosion rate highlight the impact of exposure duration and possible material behaviour changes over time. The initial increase in corrosion rate for sample-2 and sample 3 may be due to surface reactions intensifying as corrosion progresses. Such findings are critical for understanding material longevity and selecting appropriate corrosion-resistant materials for different environments.

Table 3 Immersion corrosion test result

Sl. No	Immersion test	Corrosion rate (g/hr)
1	sample-1 (24 hrs)	0.011083
2	sample-2 (48 hrs)	0.018229
3	sample-3 (72 hrs)	0.022042

3.2 Comparison of corrosion rate with immersion and electrochemical corrosion study

Electrochemical Corrosion experiment is one of the predominant methods to evaluate the corrosion rate of a material. This process analysis through which materials, typically metals, degrade as a result of electrochemical reactions. It usually occurs when a metal is exposed to a corrosive environment, such as sea water, air, or other reactive substances. This process involves the transformation of the metal from a solid state to a dissolved ion, accompanied by the release of electrons. The electrochemical corrosion process is driven by the formation of an anode and a cathode on the metal surface. The anode is where the metal undergoes oxidation (loses electrons), and the cathode is where reduction reactions (gaining electrons) take place. The environment in which the corrosion occurs, typically water or another ionic medium (such as acid or salt solutions). The electrolyte facilitates the movement of ions between the anode and cathode. P A Amalan A et al. 2022 [2] studied electrochemical corrosion behavior of magnesium alloy AZ91 and reported the corrosion rate of T6 ageing heat treated sample is 0.071 mm/yr. Present experimental results agreed with electrochemical results.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this present work, AZ91 magnesium alloy was prepared through stir casting method. The microstructure and immersion corrosion properties were studied through experimentally in atmospheric condition. The following outcomes were listed below.

- i) Stir casting process is one of the conventional and economical method for preparing the magnesium-based materials.
- ii) XRD study validates the presence of α -Mg phase and the secondary $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ intermetallic phases.
- iii) SEM morphology showed the uniform surface morphology of produced alloy.
- iv) The immersion corrosion study had been carried out for one day, two days and three days immersion duration.
- v) The corrosion rate for the sample – 1 (24 hrs) is 0.011083 g/hr and for sample -3 (72 hrs) is 0.022042 g/hr.
- vi) The overall observation of this study demonstrated appropriate corrosion-resistant materials or secondary process is required to improve better corrosion resistance for corrosion environmental applications

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. Saikrishna, G. P. K. Reddy, B. Munirathinam, R. Dumpala, M. Jagannatham, and B. R. Sunil, 2018 “An investigation on the hardness and corrosion behavior of MWCNT/Mg composites and grain refined Mg,” J. Magnes. Alloy., vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 83–89.

- [2] Packia Antony Amalan, A., Sivaram, N.M., Bavatharani, C. and Ragupathy, D., 2022. A study on the effect of ageing heat treatment on hardness, tensile and corrosion behaviour of stir-cast AZ91D–5SiC–1Gr hybrid magnesium composite. *International Journal of Metalcasting*, 16(2), pp.973-986.
- [3] Palaniappan, N., Cole, I.S., Kuznetsov, A., Thomas, K.J., Ruszkowski, P. and Kujawska, M., 2022. Experimental and DFT studies of selenium decorated graphene oxide: Redox stability, cytotoxicity, and corrosion inhibition of AZ13 Mg alloy. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 292, p.126870.
- [4] Sultana, R., Kékedy-Nagy, L., Daneshpour, R. and Greenlee, L.F., 2022. Electrochemical recovery of phosphate from synthetic waste water with enhanced salinity. *Electrochimica Acta*, 426, p.140848.
- [5] Liu, Z., Yue, H., Zhu, J. and Han, J., 2025. In Vivo Degradation Behavior of AZ91 Magnesium Alloy: Comprehensive Microstructural and Crystallographic Characterization by TEM and NBED. *Materials*, 18(7), p.1500.
- [6] Zhang, Y., Yan, C., Wang, F. and Li, W., 2005. Electrochemical behavior of anodized Mg alloy AZ91D in chloride containing aqueous solution. *Corrosion Science*, 47(11), pp. 2816-2831.
- [7] Pardo, A., Merino, M.C., Coy, A.E., Arrabal, R., Viejo, F. and Matykina, E., 2008. Corrosion behaviour of magnesium/aluminium alloys in 3.5 wt.% NaCl. *Corrosion Science*, 50(3), pp.823-834.
- [8] Sun, S., Zheng, Q., Li, D. and Wen, J., 2009. Long-term atmospheric corrosion behaviour of aluminium alloys 2024 and 7075 in urban, coastal and industrial environments. *Corrosion Science*, 51(4), pp.719-727.
- [9] Liu, Y., Tang, X., Zeng, Q., Liu, B., Lai, J., Jin, J. and Li, S., 2024. Experimental and theoretical study on corrosion mechanism of aluminium alloy in different corrosive solutions. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 412, p.125894.
- [10] Proton, V., Alexis, J., Andrieu, E., Delfosse, J., Deschamps, A., De Geuser, F., Lafont, M.C. and Blanc, C., 2014. The influence of artificial ageing on the corrosion behaviour of a 2050 aluminium–copper–lithium alloy. *Corrosion Science*, 80, pp.494-502.
- [11] Ujah, C.O., Kallon, D.V. and Aigbodion, V.S., 2024. Corrosion characteristics of high-entropy alloys prepared by spark plasma sintering. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 132(1), pp.63-82.
- [12] Uerdingen, M., Treber, C., Balser, M., Schmitt, G. and Werner, C., 2005. Corrosion behaviour of ionic liquids. *Green Chemistry*, 7(5), pp.321-325.
- [13] Patel, N.S., Pavlík, V. and Boča, M., 2017. High-temperature corrosion behavior of superalloys in molten salts—a review. *Critical Reviews in Solid State and Materials Sciences*, 42(1), pp.83-97.
- [14] Cabeza, L.F., Illa, J., Roca, J., Badia, F., Mehling, H., Hiebler, S. and Ziegler, F., 2001. Immersion corrosion tests on metal-salt hydrate pairs used for latent heat storage in the 32 to 36 C temperature range. *Materials and corrosion*, 52(2), pp.140-146.